

COMPETENCY APPROACH IN ELEMENTARY MATHEMATICS CLASSES

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Abstract. *This article is based on the passage of elementary mathematics based on the competence approach. Also, comments on the competency approach in elementary grades were given and types of competency were noted. In addition, the system of mathematics lessons in elementary grades - Students are treated with several concepts in each lesson. Each of them can be mastered at different stages of this lesson.*

Keywords: *competence, communicative competence, competence to work with information, competence of self-development, competence of socially active citizen, national and general cultural competence, competence to be aware of news.*

In our republic, the concept of developing the public education system until 2030 was approved, five initiatives, including comprehensive measures and activities aimed at creating additional conditions for youth education, were put into practice, the competence approach of general secondary education was implemented based state educational standards and science curricula were developed, normative frameworks for participation in international studies on the assessment of educational quality were created. Education based on the competence approach is characterized by the preparation of students to use the acquired information in standard and non-standard situations of educational and life activities. Adapting school education to the requirements of modern development, improving electronic educational resources in subjects, ensuring active communication of students with electronic resources, implementing independent education and self-assessment, actively searching for the necessary information and it implies the formation of competences for its use in solving emerging problems. Education based on the competence approach is characterized by the preparation of students to use the acquired information in standard and non-standard situations of educational and life activities.

Adapting school education to the requirements of modern development, improving electronic educational resources in subjects, ensuring active communication of students with electronic resources, implementing independent education and self-assessment, actively searching for the necessary information and it implies the formation of competences for its use in solving emerging problems. The main essence of teaching based on the competence approach is to use the knowledge, skills and abilities acquired by students in the course of education, which is organized from vocational subjects, in their personal life, as well as in their future professional and social activities. orientation to the formation of acquisition competencies is considered. It is necessary for students to engage in personal, social, economic and professional relationships during their future life, to take their place in society, to solve the problems they face in this process, and most importantly, to be competitive in their field and profession. Competencies formed in students are divided into three levels: basic competencies; general (subject) competencies; private competencies. Competencies that create a foundation for the general development of a student's personality are called basic competencies, and competencies that are formed only through the subject of study are called special competencies. There are different definitions and approaches to

the word competence. In particular, the word competence is explained in the "National Encyclopedia of Uzbekistan" as follows: competence (lat. Compete - I'm achieving, I'm worthy, I'm worthy) - a specific state body (local self-government body) or an official's law, charter or scope of powers, rights and duties defined by another document; knowledge, experience in this or that field. The term "competence" in a broad sense means the ability to apply knowledge and skills based on practical experience and act successfully in solving common problems. It comes from the Latin "campetere" - to be compatible. Competence is a sign of activity that leads to an expected result. It is a product of knowledge, and it is the ability of an expert to put it into practice. The difference between competence and knowledge is that it cannot be defined or evaluated without practical performance of the task. Skill is an important criterion of competence, which is manifested as a result of repeated application in various situations, including problem situations. In the Republic of Uzbekistan, based on the continuity and integrity of education, the priority of the student's personality and interests, the following basic competencies are formed in accordance with their age characteristics. Communicative competence means the ability to communicate in the native language and any foreign language in social situations, to follow the culture of communication, social flexibility, and the ability to work effectively in a team.

Competence to work with information means the ability to search for, sort, process, store, and effectively use information from media sources, ensure their security, and develop the ability to acquire media culture. Self-development competence - continuous physical, spiritual, mental, intellectual and creative development of oneself, striving for perfection, independent learning throughout life, cognitive skills and life experience implies acquiring the skills of independent regular improvement, alternative evaluation of one's own behavior and ability to make independent decisions.

Socially active citizenship competence - to feel involvement in the events, events and processes taking place in society and to actively participate in them, to know one's civic duties and rights, to comply with them, to have the ability to deal with labor and civil relations and acquire legal culture implies. National and universal cultural competence means the formation of the ability to be loyal to the motherland, be kind to people and believe in universal and national values, to understand works of art and works of art, to dress appropriately, to follow cultural rules and a healthy lifestyle.

Mathematical literacy, awareness of scientific and technical innovations and the competence to use them - to be able to make personal, family, professional and economic plans based on accurate calculations, to be able to read various diagrams, drawings and models in daily activities, to ease human labor, to work. It implies the formation of abilities to use scientific and technical innovations that increase productivity and lead to favorable conditions. These competencies are formed in students through general education subjects. Also, based on the content of each subject of general education, general competences related to the subject are formed in the students. The science of mathematics develops a person's intellect and attention, educates determination and will to achieve the intended goal, ensures algorithmic discipline and expands his thinking. Mathematics is the basis of knowledge of the universe, and it is important for the development of production, science and technology, revealing the specific laws of surrounding events and phenomena.

The main goal of teaching mathematics in primary education is to form and develop the system of mathematical knowledge and skills necessary for students to use in daily activities, to

learn subjects and to continue their education. formation of a person who can successfully operate in a developing society, who can think clearly and clearly, critically and logically, appreciate the national, spiritual and cultural heritage, form a person who can think about the rational use of natural and material resources, appreciate the national, spiritual and cultural heritage, rational use and preservation of natural and material resources, education of mathematical culture as a component of universal culture. Competency approach is important in ensuring that students acquire knowledge and skills about mathematical concepts, properties, forms, methods and algorithms. Understanding the importance of mathematics in human development and social development, socio-economic relations, teaching to successfully apply mathematical knowledge and skills in everyday life, developing individual characteristics of students, forming independent learning skills, integration of subjects taking into account the competence approach is important in the formation of national and universal values, creativity in students and in guiding them to consciously choose a profession.

A lesson is a historical, complex form of organizing mathematics teaching at school, verified by many years of experience and meeting the basic requirements of the present time. Students' acquisition of mathematical knowledge depends not only on choosing the right method in the study, but also on the form of organization of the educational process. A lesson is an educational work organized by a fixed number of students under the guidance of a teacher, based on a specific schedule, according to the program. During the lesson, students learn theoretical information from mathematics, calculation skills, problem solving, various measurements, that is, all educational work is done in the lesson. The unique aspects of the mathematics lesson, first of all, arise from the characteristics of this educational subject. One of its features is that, along with arithmetic material, elements of algebra and geometry are also studied. Another unique feature of the elementary course of mathematics is the combined consideration of theoretical and practical issues. That's why practical skills and skills are inculcated in each lesson with the introduction of new knowledge. Usually, several didactic goals are implemented in the lesson: passing new material; strengthening of knowledge related to the subject; summarizing and systematizing them; building solid learning and skills, etc. Another feature of mathematics lessons is the abstract nature of the learning material. Therefore, it also depends on visual aids, careful selection of active methods of teaching, student activity, level of mastery of class students. Another requirement for modern mathematics classes is to develop students' independent thinking and creative activity. Mental operations such as analysis, synthesis, comparison, generalization, drawing conclusions are formed in the student.

The system of mathematics lessons in elementary grades - Students work with several concepts in each lesson. Each of them can be mastered at different stages of this lesson. The understanding of each concept is carried out by repeating and recalling another concept, and this concept serves to explain the next concepts. In the course of teaching, each educational material is carried out in a developed manner, this educational material is the foundation for understanding the materials taught after it. If we look at the process of mastering another concept, it is formed as a result of interrelated teaching of several lessons. In this way, the formation of mathematical concepts is formed not in one lesson, but in the process of passing a number of interconnected lessons. We call such classes a system of joint classes.

Therefore, the teacher should place the lessons in a logical sequence that reveal the content of the subject. The biggest requirement in the structure of the lesson system is to take into account

the educational purpose of the lesson, to take into account the methodological and general pedagogical aspects of teaching principles. A well-thought-out system of lessons on the topic depends on the correct distribution of study time to topics. It should focus on creating students' independence, reviewing specific examples, drawing specific conclusions, and drawing general conclusions from them. After acquiring and strengthening this knowledge in the lesson system, examples and problems should be solved. After that, it is necessary to re-increase the skills with the help of exercises, as well as to ensure that the acquired knowledge is always brought into one system and generalized. The following main stages are important in determining the content of a certain topic of the program, in distributing the subject material to class times, that is, in mastering knowledge. 1. Preparation of new material for teaching. 2. Perception of new educational material and formation of new knowledge. 3. Consolidation of knowledge and formation of skills through various exercises. One of the important requirements of the present time is to activate the knowledge and creative activities of students. Each lesson should be focused on thinking and creativity.

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